

Simplified mini-prep method for *Taq* DNA polymerase extraction

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The need for the use of molecular biology reagents has been increasing day by day. In addition to commercially provided molecular biology reagents, some and/or most reagents could be also produced in specific investigation laboratories manually. In this study, we aimed to extract *Taq* DNA polymerase enzyme by ethanol precipitation method within a short time and cost-effectively. For this purpose, first, we cloned the pOpenTaq plasmid with *Taq* (*polA*) gene into *Escherichia coli* JM107 strain. Confirmed transformants were subjected to *Taq* DNA polymerase extraction. Transformants were grown at 37°C for 16 hours in LBB with ampicillin (100 µg/mL). Then, cells were induced by 1 mM IPTG supplement and incubated overnight again. Lysozyme (10 mg/mL; 1:1000 V:V) and DNaseI (10 mg/mL; 1:20000 V:V) treatments were used in the extraction steps. The purification was carried out with a total use of 70% ethanol. Totally 50 µL of protein was obtained after a three-day protocol. In SDS-PAGE assays, approximately 94 kDa protein was checked and then used in PCR analysis. *Taq* DNA polymerase was used in the amplification of *tef1-α* and 28S rDNA in *Fusarium graminearum* genome. Both genes were amplified from the *F. graminearum* genome by using a common PCR protocol. The findings obtained from this study showed that the ethanol precipitation method could be easily adapted to *Taq* DNA polymerase extraction within a short time in specific laboratories which involve common equipment.

Keywords: *E. coli*, enzyme, Mini-prep, PCR, *Taq* DNA polymerase

INTRODUCTION

Kary Mullis invented the PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) technology in 1983, which operates on the basis of fast replication of specific nucleic acid regions (Mullis, et al., 1983). PCR technique is utilized in a variety of applications, including gene cloning, gene expression analysis, and polymorphism analysis (McPherson and Møller, 2000; Temizkan ve Arda, 2004; Temizkan, 2021; Yörük, 2021).

The *Taq* DNA Polymerase enzyme was first obtained from the thermophilic bacteria *Thermus aquaticus*. *polA* gene was successfully cloned in the *Escherichia coli* bacterium, and then recombinant *Taq* DNA polymerase types have been used in PCR applications currently (Saiki, et al., 1988; Grimm and Arbutnot, 1995). Engelke's lab. extracted the *Taq* DNA polymerase enzyme, then purified it using polyethyleneimine and desalinated it by dialysis assays (Engelke et. al., 1990). This method needed a lengthy process in terms of both expense and time. *Taq* Pol I enzyme was precipitated using ammonium sulfate in later studies, and dialysis was no longer necessary due to adjustments made in the

storage buffer (Pluthero, 1993).

Dr. Sun and his colleagues reported that the activity of the enzyme created using this approach (ammonium sulfate-based precipitation) was reduced by 30-40% and that the enzyme included a minor number of DNA molecules. Furthermore, investigations have demonstrated that ethanol is an effective solvent (Chen et. al., 2015).

Despite the fact that *Taq* DNA polymerase has been extracted and used commercially for many years, *Taq* DNA polymerase remains an expensive product for many laboratories. In this work, we aimed to conduct and optimize Dr. Sun's method for producing *Taq* DNA Polymerase I enzyme with fewer components and labor using the mini-prep protocol. We believe that the protocol provided in this study will make it easier to create the enzyme and will aid laboratories in their future research.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plasmids and cells: The pOpenTaq Plasmid (code: 5262_11) with *Taq* (*polA*) gene was a gift from Prof. Dr. Drew Endy at Stanford University. *Escherichia coli* JM107 strain was used in bacterial

transformation studies. *Fusarium graminearum* PH-1 strain was used in PCR assays.

***E. coli* transformation:** Common CaCl₂-based transformation protocols were followed in the transformation of the plasmid-free *E. coli* JM107 strain. For this purpose, 50 mL of LBB (Luria Bertani Broth) was inoculated with *E. coli* JM107 strain. After 16-hour incubation at a rotary shaker with 180 rpm (37°C), competent cells were obtained. Up to 1 µg plasmids were transformed into 100 µL competent *E. coli* cells. The cells were subjected to common heat shock processes and then were poured onto LBA (Luria Bertani Agar) plates with 100 µg/mL ampicillin (Lederberg and Cohen, 1974; Nishimura et al., 1990). After 16-hour incubation at 37°C, bacterial colonies were selected by colony PCR using common M13 cloning primer sets with a standard protocol (Woodman, 2008; Bergkessel and Guthrie, 2013). Bacterial colonies with single PCR bands of approximately 610 bp were selected for further studies.

***Taq* DNA polymerase expression, extraction, and purification:** Common protocols for *Taq* DNA polymerase obtaining were slightly modified in this study (Engelke et al., 1990; Pluthero, 1993). 25 µL of transformant cells were transferred into the LBB medium of 5 mL LBB including 5 µL (100 mg/mL) ampicillin and the cells were left in a shaker for 16 hours at 37°C and 160 rpm. 0.2 mL cells were then grown in 10 mL LBB including 10 µL (100 mg/mL) ampicillin for 5 hours at 37°C and 160 rpm. 1 mM IPTG (with concentration) was added to the culture, and then the cells were grown for 12 hours at 37°C and 160 rpm. The cells were centrifugated at 12,000 rpm (+4°C) for 10 min, and the supernatant was removed.

In the extraction step, 0.5 mL of buffer A (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.9; 50 mM dextrose, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM PMSF) was added to the pellets, and it was mixed well. 50 µL of lysozyme (10 mg/mL, 1:1000 V:V) was added to the mixture and it was carefully mixed. The cells were centrifugated at 12,000 rpm (+4°C) for 10 min, and they were suspended with 0.5 mL buffer A. The samples were incubated at -20°C for 30 min and room temperature (RT) for 5 min twice. 25 µL of lysozyme (10 mg/mL) was added after freezing at -20°C and thawing in RT, and the mixture was kept at RT for 15 min. An equal volume of buffer B (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.9; 50 mM KCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM DTT, 1 mM PMSF, 0.5% Tween 20, 0.5% Nonidet P40) was added to the mixture. The cells were incubated at 75°C for 30 min. The samples were centrifugated at 12,000 rpm (+4°C) for 15 min. When the mixtures were left at RT, the cells, 1% buffer C (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5; 15 mM NaCl, 2 mM CaCl₂, 100 mM MgCl₂, 50% glycerol,

0.5 mg/mL DNase I, 10 mg/mL RNase A) and 0.5 mM PMSF (from 100 mM PMSF) were added to the mixture. The samples were incubated at RT for 5 min, and 30 min at 75°C. The samples were centrifugated at 12,000 rpm (+4°C) for 15 min, and the supernatant was transferred to a new tube. The mixture including 55% of ethanol with final concentration was obtained. The mixture was centrifugated at 12,000 rpm (+4°C) for 20 min. The samples were dissolved in 250 µL of buffer C (50 mM Tris-Cl, 50 mM NaCl, 0.1 mM EDTA, 1 mM DTT, 0.5 mM PMSF, 10% glycerol; pH 8.6) and stored at -20°C.

Validation of *Taq* DNA polymerase extraction: BCA kit (Atlas-Biyoteknoloji, Turkey) was used in order to determine the concentration of protein extracts. Up to 1 mg of protein was loaded onto gels. The presence of *Taq* DNA polymerase protein in buffer C was validated by running the samples at 6% SDS-PAGE gels with common protocols (Temizkan and Arda, 2004). Approximately 90 kDa protein was checked by using a protein ladder (PINK Plus Prestained Protein Ladder, GeneDirex).

In PCR analysis, common for fungal identification primers ITS5-NL4 set, ITS5 (5'-ggaagtaaagtcgtaacaagg-3') and NL4 (5'-ggt ccgtgttcaagacgg-3'), was used in *F. graminearum* genome to verify if *Taq* DNA polymerase extracted in this study works or not. Common PCR protocol (Yörük, 2021) was followed in PCR assays using a *Taq* DNA polymerase obtained in this study 0.5 µL, accompanied by PCR buffers and other components provided by Thermo *Taq* DNA polymerase kit (EP0402). PCR band of approximately 1.2 kb was detected on agarose gels of 1.2% under the U.V. transilluminator (Hi-Media, India).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, protocols provided from previous studies (Engelke et al., 1990; Pluthero, 1993; Chen et al., 2015) were adapted to the mini-prep protocol with slight modifications. In contrast to these studies, it was shown that *Taq* DNA polymerase could be obtained within a small volume by developing mini-prep protocol. For this purpose, up to 1.7 mg/mL of protein was obtained after extraction protocols. Approximately 90 kDa enzyme was detected on 6% SDS-PAGE gels (Fig. 1).

This enzyme (with 0.5 µL) was used in a common PCR identification protocol. PCR analysis of ITS5-NL4 yielded the expected 1.2 kb amplicon (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. 6% SDS-PAGE profile of Taq DNA polymerase band. M: Protein ladder (GeneDirex), S: Taq DNA polymerase obtained in this study.

Fig. 2. 1.2 agarose gel profile of ITS5-NL4 band from *F. graminearum* genome band. M: 1 kb DNA ladder (Thermo), S: PCR band of ITS5-NL4, and NC: no template control

The use of organic solvents and analytical methods is well-known and widely used in protein purification protocols. On the other hand, organic solvents and post-technical procedures such as chromatography types could influence the quality, quantity, and stability of the proteins which are expected to be extracted (Ghosh, 2006; Chen et al., 2015). In this study, ethanol precipitation-based protocol was adapted to mini-prep volumes. No low level of protein was obtained using ethanol precipitation in this study. Due to its wide range of usage in molecular biology investigations, such as nucleic acid extraction procedures, solvent for secondary metabolites, easy availability, and relative cost-effectiveness, ethanol usage-based *Taq* DNA polymerase obtained via mini prep protocol could be useful in any molecular biology laboratory worldwide.

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Taq DNT polimerazanın ekstraksiyası üçün sadələşdirilmiş mini hazırlıq üsulu

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Molekulyar biologiya reagentlərinin istifadəsinə ehtiyac günü-gündən artır. Kommersiya olaraq təqdim edilən molekulyar biologiya reagentlərinə əlavə olaraq, bəzi və/və ya əksər reagentlər xüsusi tədqiqat laboratoriyalarında manual olaraq da istehsal oluna bilər. Bu tədqiqatdakı məqsədimiz. Taq DNT polimeraza fermentini etanol çökdürmə üsulu ilə qısa müddətdə və sərfəli şəkildə çıxarmaqdır. Bu məqsədlə əvvəlcə biz pOpenTaq plazmidini Taq (polA) geni ilə *Escherichia coli* JM107 ştamına klonladıq. Təsdiqlənmiş transformantlar Taq DNT polimeraz ekstraksiyasına məruz qalmışdır. Transformantlar ampisilin (100 µg/mL) ilə LBB-də 16 saat ərzində 37°C-də yetişdirilmişdir. Sonra, hüceyrələr 1 mM IPTG əlavəsi ilə induksiya edildi və yenidən bir gecədə inkubasiya edildi. Ekstraksiya mərhələlərində lizozimdən (10 mg/mL; 1:1000 V:V) və DNaseI (10 mg/mL; 1:20000 V:V) istifadə edilmişdir. Təmizləmə cəmi 70% etanol istifadəsi ilə aparılmışdır. Üç günlük protokoldan sonra cəmi 50 µL protein əldə edildi. SDS-PAGE analizlərində təxminən 94 kDa zülal yoxlanıldı və sonra PCR analizində istifadə edildi. Taq DNT polimerazı *Fusarium graminearum* genomunda *tef1-α* və 28SrDNA-nın gücləndirilməsində istifadə edilmişdir. Hər iki gen ümumi PCR protokolundan istifadə etməklə *F. graminearum* genomundan gücləndirilmişdir. Bu tədqiqatdan əldə edilən nəticələr göstərdi ki, etanol çökdürmə metodu ümumi avadanlıqları əhatə edən xüsusi laboratoriyalarda qısa müddət ərzində Taq DNT polimeraz ekstraksiyasına asanlıqla adaptasiya ola bilər.

Açar sözlər: *E. coli, ferment, Mini-prep, PZR, Taq DNT polimeraza*